

A Cooperative DRL Approach for Autonomous Traffic Prioritization in Mixed Vehicles Scenarios

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Abstract—The number of connected and automated vehicles in urban areas will gradually increase in the near future. As a consequence, mixed traffic made of both regular human-driven and connected and automated vehicles will likely be a typical scenario over the next few years. Connected and automated vehicles can benefit the whole traffic experience by preventing collisions and optimizing traffic waves. In this context, unsignalized intersection management is one of the most critical challenge. However, it has received less attention in recent literature. In this paper, we introduce a novel approach to optimize traffic flow at unsignalized intersections by using cooperative deep reinforcement learning. In the proposed multi-agent strategy, each connected automated vehicle (CAV) acts as an agent and has partial observability of the current state made of other CAVs, regular vehicles and priority connected vehicles (CPV), such as ambulances and police cars. The ultimate goal of each agent is to give right-of-way to priority vehicles, prevent collisions and optimize intersection crossing time. Experimental results of the simulations carried out in SUMO on randomly generated traffic validate the presented approach and show the performance and the safety of the final trained policy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The constant increase of urban mobility over the past decades has improved the overall quality of life around the world. At the same time, when it comes to urban environments, various problems have been arising such as traffic congestion, collisions and pollution. As a consequence, continuous efforts are required to optimize traffic flow, reduce travel time, decrease fuel consumption and prevent collisions.

Among urban routes infrastructures, intersections represent one of the major bottlenecks of traffic flow [1]. Moreover, according to a report published by the U.S. Transportation Department, about 40% of all collisions occur at or nearby intersections [2].

A concrete chance to contribute to traffic flow optimization in critical areas, such as intersections, is being recently given by the advent of connected and automated vehicles (CAV). The capability of those vehicles to exchange data by a Vehicle-to-Vehicle or Vehicle-to-Grid infrastructure makes it possible to implement different classes of optimization tasks and therefore schedule crossing times based on priorities, prevent collisions and ultimately improve traffic streams.

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In this context, most of the literature has been focusing on optimal intersections management under full CAV environment, considering signalized and unsignalized intersections and using mostly rule-based and optimization methodologies with the support of simulators and numerical tests [3].

However, as the reality in the near future will be a mixture of CAV and regular vehicles (RV), mixed traffic scenarios have been recently receiving more attention. In this regard, in [4], the authors analyze the existing solutions for intersection management under mixed traffic environments at signalized intersections but point out that a full connected environment is often a requirement for the proposed methods to be effectively applied. Moreover, they conclude that Machine Learning (ML) approaches, thanks to their capability of continuous learning and adaption, can be an alternative reliable approach when it comes to hybrid environments in which not all vehicles are connected.

Among ML techniques, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has proved to be a powerful learning framework, capable of learning complex policies in high dimensional environments, and it has been recently employed in literature for different applications in the domain of Autonomous Driving [5], [6], [7].

More specifically, in [8], a novel approach for unsignalized intersection management is proposed that is based on a DRL-based centralized policy that optimizes traffic flow and arranges the right-of-way between vehicles. A method that combines 2D Lidar sensors observations and DRL in a game-theoretic decision-making context is proposed in [9]. The authors claim that their technique enables vehicles to make optimal decisions at unsignalized intersections without using any central coordinator or vehicle-to-vehicle infrastructure. A similar approach for complex intersection scenarios is proposed in [10], in which DRL is supported by long short-term memory (LSTM) that processes traffic images collected by a camera sensor mounted on the vehicle.

In addition, several recent works exist that employ Multi-agent DRL techniques for autonomous intersection management in a decentralized a cooperative fashion and show promising results in optimizing traffic flow, prevent collisions, decrease fuel consumption and reduce vehicles waiting time [11], [12].

However, among existing works, unsignalized intersection management in mixed traffic scenarios has received very little attention. Moreover, at the best of our knowledge, none of the existing works consider that vehicles may have different priorities based on their class. For example, an ambulance or a police car must be given the right-of-way by

all other autonomous or regular vehicles in order to safely cross the intersection.

Motivated by this gap, in this paper, we introduce a novel Multi-agent Cooperative DRL approach for autonomous intersection management at unsignalized intersections under prioritized mixed traffic scenarios. In the proposed method, three different vehicle classes are considered: Connected Automated Vehicles, i.e. CAVs, that act as agents, Connected Priority Vehicles (CPVs), such as ambulances or police cars, that are connected but driven by humans and, lastly, Regular Vehicles (RVs), that are neither connected or automated. In detail, the main contributions of this work are:

- (i) A novel state representation of mixed traffic consisting of four overlapped grid layers representing the current route of each CAV or CPV connected vehicle, the speed, the distance to the intersection and, eventually, the distance from the vehicle in front, which could be even an unconnected vehicle. As a consequence, since RVs are not connected, the current traffic state is only partially observable by the agents.
- (ii) A weighted global reward function that considers CAVs and CPVs current speeds at each step and applies strong penalties in case of collisions.
- (iii) A Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [13] approach to find the optimal DRL-based policy that optimizes traffic flow by observing vehicles priorities, preventing collisions and reducing crossing times.

Compared to previous works, the main challenge addressed by the proposed DRL algorithm is to instruct the CAVs to take into account the class to which each other vehicle approaching the intersection belongs and to act accordingly.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the problem of autonomous intersection management problem at unsignalized intersections under prioritized mixed traffic scenarios is formulated and the resulting system is modeled. Section III introduces the Multi-agent Cooperative DRL approach to automate intersection management. In Section IV, a case study designed in SUMO [14] and trained by RLlib [15] shows the performance of the proposed method under simulated mixed traffic scenarios. Finally, Section V concludes the work and draws future research directions.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

This section describes the Autonomous Intersection Management problem (AIM) addressed in this paper and depicted in Fig. 1. In detail, three different classes of vehicles are approaching a 4-way double lane unsignalized intersection at the same time. The two red vehicles are CAVs, the blue vehicle is a CPV, for example an ambulance, whereas the yellow vehicle is a RV, which is not connected. The two CAVs wish to cross the intersection from right to left side and from left to right side respectively, while the ambulance is heading south and the RV wishes to turn left.

Since all vehicles are approaching the intersection at the same time, both a priority and a scheduling problem occur. In absence of traffic signals, one of the possible strategies

to solve such problem is to follow the traffic rules and force all vehicles to give way to the right. However, in case a vehicle has higher priority over other vehicles on the basis of its class, that approach is not always feasible. Such case is depicted in Fig. 2a. The blue priority vehicle slows down at intersection and gives right-of-way to one of the CAVs, that is not acceptable, as the blue vehicle has priority over the red one. Moreover, at unsignalized intersections, the risk of collisions is higher than at signalized intersections due to the high degree of discretionary power conferred to the drivers.

Fig. 1: Standard mixed traffic scenario at unsignalized intersection including CAVs (red), CPVs (blue) and RVs (yellow) vehicles.

In the proposed approach, CAVs and CPVs are both connected to a Vehicle-to-Infrastructure architecture and exchange data about their desired route, current lane, speed and distance to the intersection and eventually the distance from the vehicle in front, that could be even a regular vehicle.

The final objective is to design a control strategy for CAVs that regulates their speed at discrete time intervals in order to observe priorities, prevent collisions and reduce crossing times, even overcoming standard traffic rules in certain conditions. By following such ideal control strategy, we determine the scenario in Fig. 2b, in which the red vehicles, regardless of traffic rules, slow down as they know that a priority blue vehicle is about to cross the intersection.

In that respect, in this work, the control strategy is designed in terms of a policy trained by a DRL algorithm in a simulation framework. Accordingly, to model the interaction between CAVs and other vehicles, we model the AIM problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), where the agents follow a policy $\pi(a|s)$ in a predetermined environment. More specifically, at each time step t , given the current state $s(t)$, each agent chooses an action $a(t) \in \mathcal{A}$, according to the current policy, transits to the next state $s(t+1)$ and finally receives a reward $r(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. The agent purpose is to maximize the expectation of the return over time that is called the discounted cumulative reward and is defined as $G(s(t)) = \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \gamma^h r(t+h+1)$, where $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ is the discount factor.

In the proposed problem formulation, the agents are the CAVs and the current state of each agent at each time step is designed on the basis of real-time traffic data shared by all connected vehicles. However, since priority vehicles are

(a) without priority

(b) with priority

Fig. 2: Mixed traffic scenario with and without CPVs priority.

connected but driven by humans and regular vehicles are also unconnected, the future state of the environment not only depends on the agents, but also on certain unknown processes, such as the future intentions of CPVs drivers and the position of RVs. As a consequence, the process is only partially observable.

In contrast, the global reward at each step is calculated on the basis of global traffic flow optimization objectives and considers both CAVs and CPVs current speeds and possible collisions. In this respect, in the proposed model, the agents work cooperatively to grant priorities, avoid accidents and reduce their crossing time.

III. MULTI-AGENT DRL OPTIMIZATION APPROACH

In this section, we introduce the details of the proposed Multi-agent DRL approach for AIM. For the sake of simplicity, we assume a 4-way unsignalized intersection, even if the method can be generalized to any kind of intersection.

A. Intersection scheme

The considered 4-way intersection is schematized in Fig. 3. Each way is made of two double lanes identified by a unique label. The first label identifies the incoming lane to the intersection, whereas the second one spots the outgoing lane. All possible routes are represented by the arrows and can be identified by joining the incoming and outgoing lanes labels. For example, considering E1 as incoming way, vehicles can designate either E1-N2, E1-W1 or E1-S1 as their planned routes.

In addition, we define:

- $C = \{CAV_1, CAV_2, CAV_i, \dots, CAV_n\}$ as the set of CAV agents,
- $P = \{CPV_1, CPV_2, CPV_j, \dots, CPV_m\}$ as the set of CPV vehicles.

Similarly to the work [16], the intersection is divided in two different zones: (i) the control zone in which each CAV_i or CPV_j communicates with the centralized infrastructure and (ii) the merging zone where the collisions in the intersection may occur. The control zone is depicted in Fig. 3 as the gray rectangle surrounding the intersection. We assume that this zone extends up to 100 meters from the intersection center. On the contrary, the merging zone is the area shared by the

vehicles when they cross the intersection and is depicted by the dotted rectangle in Fig. 3.

Within the control zone, at every time step t , each CAV_i sends the following data to the centralized infrastructure:

- the planned route, for example: E1-N2;
- the current speed $v_i(t)$ in m/s;
- the current distance $d_i(t)$ in meters to the intersection;
- the current distance $l_i(t)$ in meters from the in front vehicle.

In the same way, the planned route, $\hat{v}_j(t)$, $\hat{d}_i(t)$ and $\hat{l}_i(t)$ are defined for each CPV_j to denote the current speed and distances to the intersection and the in front vehicle, respectively.

Fig. 3: 4-way Intersection Scheme.

B. State Representation

Having collected all data from CAVs and CPVs, the observation for each CAV_i agent at every time step t , is designed as a space in four dimensions. Every dimension in the space is a $k \times k$ grid, where k is the number of roads that make the intersection. In each $k \times k$ grid, rows and columns represent the incoming and outgoing ways

TABLE I: Observation Example for CAV_1

	N2	S1	W1	E2		N2	S1	W1	E2
N1					N1				
S2	CPV ₁		CAV ₁		S2	7m/s		9m/s	
W2		CAV ₂			W2		6m/s		
E1					E1				

I (a) I (b)

Planned Route Current Speed

	N2	S1	W1	E2		N2	S1	W1	E2
N1					N1				
S2	30m		25m		S2	n/d		6.5m	
W2		20m			W2		n/d		
E1					E1				

I (c) I (d)

Distance to Intersection Distance from Vehicle in Front

respectively, whereas each cell identifies the corresponding route as defined in Section III-A.

The four dimensions are used by CAVs and CPVs to mark in corresponding cells their planned routes, current speeds, distances to intersection and distances from the vehicle in front respectively.

In Table I, an example observation of agent CAV_1 , in the example 4-way intersection scenario, is shown.

In the proposed example, white cells of the tables represent all feasible routes on the intersection. On the contrary, gray boxes mark the unfeasible routes and cannot be filled. As shown in Table I (a), agents CAV_1 and CAV_2 (red), and priority vehicle CPV_1 (blue), have S2-W1, W2-S1 and S2-N2 as their planned routes respectively.

For each of the vehicles, the current speed in m/s is reported in Table I (b), while the distance to the intersection can be found in Table I (c). In this regard, positive values are used as the vehicle approaches the intersection, whereas negative values indicate that the vehicle is leaving the junction. Finally, in Table I (d), the distance from vehicle in front, if any, is recorded. In the given example, only CAV_1 agent has vehicle in front that could be another CAV agent, a CPV or even a regular vehicle.

In general, the proposed approach can reproduce only partially the current state traffic as each agent has only visibility of the first connected traffic vehicle in front, either CAV or CPV, for each route. Moreover, regular unconnected vehicles can be seen only in terms of their distance from a connected vehicle.

In addition, since more than one CAV may have the same planned route, agents observations generally differ each other. For example, suppose that two agents, i.e. CAV_1 and CAV_2 , both planned the same route and that CAV_2 was the vehicle in front on the way. In that case, CAV_1 would see itself in the related cell in first grid and the distance to CAV_2 would be reported in fourth grid. At the same time, in CAV_2 observation, the value in the first grid would be CAV_2 itself, whereas no distance from vehicle in front would be found in fourth grid.

Also for those reasons, the state is only partially observ-

able by each CAV agent and the cooperative approach is used to improve the performance of the trained policy.

C. Action Space

In this work, we assume that the kinematics of each autonomous CAV_i agent is driven by a separate low-level and autonomous control strategy and that only the speed $v(t)$ at each time step t needs to be set in order to fulfill the autonomous intersection management objectives.

In this regard, we define the discrete set of three actions $\mathcal{A} = \{ACC, KEEP, DEC\}$ in which, given the predefined speed variation δ m/s, one of $ACC = \delta$, $KEEP = 0$ or $DEC = -\delta$ represents the action $a_i(t)$ chosen according to the policy at every time step t for each CAV_i . As a consequence, at each step, the new speed $v_i(t)$ of the agent CAV_i is calculated as $v_i(t) = v_i(t-1) + a_i(t)$.

D. Reward

As stated in Section II, the common objectives of the proposed control strategy are: (i) force agents to observe priorities by giving right-of-way to connected priority vehicles, (ii) prevent collisions and (iii) reduce individual crossing times. In order to design a proper global reward function that takes into account all aforementioned requirements, including penalties in case of collisions, we first define the following binary variable $p_i(t)$ as follows:

$$p_i(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } CAV_i \text{ detects collisions} \\ & \text{with other vehicles at time step } t \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Then, the global reward function is defined by:

$$r(t) = w_1 \sum_{i=1}^n v_i(t) + w_2 \sum_{j=1}^m \hat{v}_j(t) - w_3 \sum_{i=1}^n v_i(t) p_i(t), \quad (2)$$

where $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in [0, 1]$ are arbitrary weights.

In detail, global reward at time step t is given by adding the weighted sum of CAVs current speeds and the weighted sum of current velocities of all priority vehicles. A more aggressive or conservative strategy against priorities is regulated by tuning w_1 , which is the weight of CAVs speeds, and w_2 , which is the weight of CPVs speeds. More specifically, greater the value of w_2 compared to w_1 , higher is the probability of CPVs to be given right-of-way by CAVs.

In addition, a strong penalty, weighted by w_3 and proportional to the current speed v_i , is applied in case CAV_i collides with other vehicles at time step t . In this respect, setting a value for $w_3 \gg w_1, w_2$ drastically increases the probability to avoid accidents.

IV. CASE STUDY

In this section, we implement the proposed method on the example scenario schematized in Fig. 3 and we give the details about the simulation environment, the training setup and the performance evaluation.

Fig. 4: Speed profile of CAV_1 and CAV_2 agents vs. priority vehicle CPV_1 as they simultaneously cross the intersection.

A. Simulation Environment and Training Setup

The intersection is designed in SUMO environment. We set three different vehicle classes: CAVs, CPVs and RVs. Then, we connect SUMO by *TraCi* interface to a Python script in which we implement the Multi-agent DRL policy training strategy by RLlib and PPO. We run 500 training episodes with randomly generated traffic on the given simulation environment and we collect some metrics.

More in detail, at the beginning of each episode, we place four vehicles at 30 meters from the intersection with randomly assigned routes. We choose to place two CAVs, i.e. the agents in the training strategy, one CPV and one RV. All vehicles are 5 meters long and have maximum speed set at 50 m/s.

As explained in Section III, a shared fully connected network (FCN) is used as policy π and value function ϕ estimator. Hence, since $k = 4$, the network, that is shown in Fig. 5, has one input layer of size $4 \times 4 \times 4 = 64$, two hidden layers of size 256 and two output layers of size 3 for the policy and 1 for the value respectively.

Although the control action on CAVs is effective as they cross the intersection, the speed should be regulated since when they approach the junction. Hence, rewards in the future are of great importance. In this regard, we set $\gamma = 0.99$ as discount factor. Moreover, we set $\alpha = 5e-5$ as starting learning rate and *ReLU* as activation function.

Finally, since we wish to give more importance to collisions prevention and CPVs crossing than to CAVs speed, we set the weights in reward function (2) as: $w_1 = 1, w_2 = 2$ and $w_3 = 5$.

To decrease the number of steps, we terminate each episode when all vehicles are on the outgoing way and at least 20 meters from the intersection. In each step, a train batch of size 4000 is sampled and chunked down in mini-batches of size 128, each of those is used to update the agents for 30 consecutive iterations. We run the simulations for 10 to 15 hours on a personal computer with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1185G7 3.00 GHz CPU and 16 GB RAM.

B. Performance Evaluation

In Fig. 6, we show the performance of the training strategy. Firstly, we observe that the global reward converges

Fig. 5: Fully Connected Network used as Policy π and Value Function ϕ estimator.

Fig. 6: Global Reward obtained during training and accumulated collisions over all episodes.

after 50 episodes to a stable value. However, after around 320 episodes the number of accumulated collisions does not significantly increase anymore. Since one of the main objectives of the proposed approach is to ensure safety and avoid accidents, both the global reward and total collisions have to be considered to determine an effective training stop strategy.

In Fig. 7, the average speed over episodes for all connected vehicles is shown. Although the speed plays a central role in reward function (2), the global average value tends to slow

Fig. 7: Average speed of connected vehicles.

down as collisions converge to a stable value around 320 episodes. This is due to the fact that CAV agents, as they approach the junction, are forced by the policy to give right-of-way to priority vehicles and to act, at the same time, in a conservative fashion to prevent collisions.

The speed profiles of CAV_1 and CAV_2 agents, compared to the one of priority vehicle CPV_1 , over a single episode after the training, are shown in Fig. 4. We observe that CAV_1 , traveling on E1-W1 route, starts slowing down after 7 seconds entering the control zone and stops for around 3 seconds at time step 9. At the same time, CAV_2 , traveling on W2-E2 route, starts decelerating after around 6 seconds and accelerates again at time step 9. In contrast, CPV_1 , traveling on N1-S1 route, constantly increases its velocity over the whole time horizon and goes through the intersection without any interference of other vehicles. In conclusion, after around 320 episodes the trained policy is able to fulfill all prescribed objectives.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a novel approach for autonomous unsignalized intersection management in mixed traffic scenarios with priority vehicles. The proposed method is based on cooperative Multi-agent Deep Reinforcement Learning and aims to optimize global traffic flow by giving right-of-way at intersection to specific classes of priority vehicles and ensuring safety, at the same time, by preventing collisions. Furthermore, since the scenario is of mixed traffic, we introduce a novel multidimensional intersection state representation that is only partially observable by each connected and autonomous vehicle since, in general, only some of other agents, priority connected vehicles and unconnected regular vehicles may appear in an observation.

We validate the proposed cooperative approach with Proximal Policy Optimization in a 4-way example scenario designed in SUMO, in which we place two connected and autonomous vehicles, one priority connected vehicle and one regular vehicle traveling on randomly assigned conflicting routes. Experiments results show that after around 320 training episodes the Fully Connected Network policy is able to ensure stable global reward, avoid accidents and give right-of-way to priority vehicles.

In future work, we plan to investigate the impact of partial observability in more complex intersections and traffic scenarios. Furthermore, we aim to assess the scalability of the presented method by extending simulations with more cooperative agents and test alternative approaches to accelerate the DRL training process.

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